

Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design Policy International Network (SPINE)

Position Paper - Synopsis¹

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Towards Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design Chemicals

Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) is becoming the foundational concept to current European 'green policies'. SPINE, an informal network of European policy makers and experts, stimulates a mindset that prioritizes safety and sustainability in industrial practices. According to SPINE, key factors for successfully implementing this approach include the abundance of (FAIR) data, a standardized SSbD approach, education, and the development of practical tools and guidance. As SPINE emphasizes, "It is the people, the inventors and engineers, who develop the solutions".

Chemicals are part and parcel of our daily life. Chemicals are used to produce the medicines that improve our health, the chemical fertilizers that boost our crop yields, the fuels that bring us where we need to go, and the isolation materials, coatings and textiles that increase our comfort. Furthermore, advanced electronics and green technologies, such as solar cells, electrolyzers and energy storage materials, incorporate a variety of chemicals. Today, tens of thousands different substances and products are central to modern life as we know it.

Some chemical substances and products, however, are persistent, toxic or contribute to climate change. Chlorofluorocarbon (CFC) refrigerants, for example, depleted the ozone layer which protects earth and its inhabitants from dangerous ultraviolet radiation. Leaded gasoline improved engine performance but exhaust gases have been linked to lower intelligence. Fossil fuels increased the amount of carbon dioxide in the atmosphere causing global warming. To protect human health, the environment and biodiversity, CFCs and leaded gasoline have been banned worldwide, and the Paris Agreement was established to phase out greenhouse gases.

New concerns about (new) chemicals, materials or products continue to emerge, for example concerns about Perfluoroalkyl and Polyfluoroalkyl Substances (PFAS), microplastics and endocrine disruptors. In its Green Deal, the European Union encourages a Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) approach to prevent unacceptable risks of (new) chemicals, materials and products. SSbD is focused on prevention, instead of remediation. It integrates safety and sustainability in the innovation and development phase and encompasses monitoring throughout the entire value chain. By shifting attention from reactive solutions to proactive risk prevention, SSbD aims to minimize harm to humanity and the planet. It is a holistic approach and an iterative process driving the continuous science-based reduction of risk.

The Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design Policy International Network (SPINE) supports a successful implementation of SSbD for chemicals, materials and products. SPINE is an informal network of experts for European policy organisations, established in 2019 to gather and share expertise in SSbD and SSbD policies. This SPINE position paper summarizes current barriers and drivers in SSbD for chemicals and provides recommendations on the ways forward towards SSbD as a standard approach in industry.

Internalizing SSbD as an obvious, necessary and basic step in innovation and development is paramount for its implementation and success. As EU president Ursula von der Leyen pointed out in

the State of the Union 2023: *“The European Green Deal provides the necessary frame, incentives, and investment – but it is the people, the inventors, the engineers who develop the solutions.”*

SSbD is also an opportunity to preserve our future prosperity and wellbeing. Successful implementation in the European Union will deliver a new, future-proof economic model for sustainable development. This will result in a European industry leading in responsible business and in business models that minimize harm to our health and environment, with focus on sustainability. Moreover, SSbD may bring reputation gains for industry and innovative power, and a reduction of risk and liabilities for harm to customers and the environment.

SPINE-members recommend:

1. **Harmonisation of an SSbD approach**, fostering the development of industry business models that actively support SSbD, and the development of harmonised voluntary SSbD approaches.
2. Facilitating the **alignment of SSbD** with existing legislation.
3. **Improved data management**, encouraging the generation and sharing of safety and sustainability (FAIR) data on chemicals, materials and products.
4. **Education and development of SSbD skills**, promoting training programs for academia, industry, policymakers, and other relevant stakeholders, and favouring research programs with a strong SSbD approach in research programmes.
5. **An SSbD ‘hub’**, creating a cross-national network and helpdesk for all stakeholders, encouraging information sharing and collaborations.
6. **An SSbD expert group**, providing reflections and advice on a coherent and holistic SSbD framework in Europe, and SSbD implementation in both private and public research and development. This group should comprise members from national authorities, academia and industry.

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